

Rhythmic Additive Property of Harmonic Expectation

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Abstract - Recently, a study has been done on searching for multiplicative property of geometric expectation. Here, attempt has been made on searching for additive property of harmonic expectation. The output obtained in the attempt has been presented in this article.

Keywords: Harmonic expectation, Discrete Random Variable, Additive Property.

1. INTRODUCTION

Expected value or expectation, a concept associated to random variable, had originally been defined as the the weighted arithmetic mean of its all possible values with their respective probabilities as the corresponding weights and termed as mathematical expectation and/or simply expectation [1 – 3 , 8 , 10 – 12]. It was termed as arithmetic expectation since it is based on arithmetic mean [4 , 6 , 15] one among the three Pythagorean means [4 , 6]. On the other hand, the concept of expectation was introduced and defined on the basis of the other two Pythagorean means namely geometric mean [4 , 6,13] and harmonic mean also [4 , 6]. The two concepts introduced on the basis of these two means were termed as geometric expectation and harmonic expectation respectively [5]. Some important and useful properties of arithmetic expectation (which is simply termed as “mathematical expectation” in the existing literature of statistics) had already been derived [8 , 9 , 11 , 14 , 16]. Recently, a study has been done on searching for multiplicative property of geometric expectation [7]. Here, attempt has been made on searching for additive property of harmonic expectation. The output obtained in the attempt has been presented in this article.

2. ADDITIVE PROPERTY OF HARMONIC EXPECTATION

Table -1: The following abbreviations/notations have been used in this article:

Abbreviation/Notation	Indication/Descri
drv	Discrete Random Variable
AE	Arithmetic Expectation
GE	Geometric Expectation
HE	Harmonic Expectation
$E_H(X)$	Harmonic Expectation of X

If a drv X assumes the values

$$x_1, x_2, \dots, \dots, x_M,$$

none of which is zero so that harmonic expectation exists, with respective probabilities

$$p_1, p_2, \dots, p_M$$

i.e. $P(X = x_i) = p_i,$

then $E_H(X)$ is defined by

$$E_H(X) = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^M p_i \cdot \frac{1}{x_i}}$$

[5], which implies,

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X}\right)} = \sum_{i=1}^M p_i \cdot x_i$$

Similarly, the harmonic expectation of another drv Y which assumes the non-zero values

$$y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N$$

with respective probabilities

$$q_1, q_2, \dots, q_N$$

i.e. $P(Y = y_j) = q_j,$

is defined by

$$E_H(Y) = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^N q_j \cdot \frac{1}{y_j}}$$

which implies,

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{Y}\right)} = \sum_{j=1}^N q_j \cdot y_j$$

Now, let us consider the variable

$$\frac{1}{X+Y}$$

if

$$P(X = x_i, Y = y_j) = r_{ij}$$

then

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X+Y}\right)} = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N r_{ij} (x_i + y_j)$$

But

$$\sum_{j=1}^N r_{ij} = \sum_{j=1}^N P(X = x_i, Y = y_j) = P(X = x_i) = p_i$$

$$\& \quad \sum_{i=1}^M r_{ij} = \sum_{i=1}^M P(X = x_i, Y = y_j) = P(Y = y_j) = q_j$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X+Y}\right)} = \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\sum_{j=1}^N r_{ij}\right) \frac{1}{x_i} + \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\sum_{i=1}^M r_{ij}\right) \frac{1}{y_j}$$

which implies,

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X+Y}\right)} = \sum_{i=1}^M p_i \frac{1}{x_i} + \sum_{j=1}^N q_j \frac{1}{y_j}$$

Hence,

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X+Y}\right)} = \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X}\right)} + \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{Y}\right)}$$

Now, if X, Y & Z are three discrete random variables such that all assume non-zero values then

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X+Y+Z}\right)} = \frac{1}{E_H\left\{\frac{1}{X+(Y+Z)}\right\}} = \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X}\right)} + \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{Y+Z}\right)}$$

Hence,

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X+Y+Z}\right)} = \frac{1}{E_H(X)} + \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{Y}\right)} + \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{Z}\right)}$$

By the application the mathematical induction, one can obtain that if

X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n

are n discrete random variables such that all assume non-zero values then

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X_1+X_2+\dots+X_n}\right)} = \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X_1}\right)} + \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X_2}\right)} + \dots + \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X_n}\right)}$$

Thus, the following theorem, interpretable as additive property of harmonic expectation, has been obtained:

Theorem (2.1):

If

X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n

are n discrete random variables such that all assume non-zero values then

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X_1+X_2+\dots+X_n}\right)} = \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X_1}\right)} + \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X_2}\right)} + \dots + \frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X_n}\right)}$$

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

Suppose that an unbiased dice is thrown once.

If X is a drv denoting the number which is the half of the number occurred in the throw then the probabilities of the values assumed by it are

$$P(X = 0.5) = 1/6, P(X = 1.0) = 1/6, P(X = 1.5) = 1/6,$$

$$P(X = 2.0) = 1/6, P(X = 2.5) = 1/6, P(X = 3.0) = 1/6.$$

In this case, it is found from calculation that

$$E_H\left(\frac{1}{X}\right) = 0.57142857142857142857142857142857$$

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{X}\right)} = 1.75$$

Similarly, if Y is another random variable denoting the number which is the quarter of the number occurred in the throw then the probabilities of the values assumed by it are

$$P(Y = 0.25) = 1/6, P(Y = 0.5) = 1/6, P(Y = 0.75) = 1/6,$$

$$P(Y = 1.0) = 1/6, P(Y = 1.25) = 1/6, P(Y = 1.5) = 1/6.$$

are all equal and is 1/6.

In this case, it is found from calculation that

$$E_H\left(\frac{1}{Y}\right) = 1.1428571428571428571428571428571$$

$$\frac{1}{E_H\left(\frac{1}{Y}\right)} = 0.875$$

Now, the probabilities of the values assumed by $\frac{1}{X+Y}$ are as follows:

$$P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 0.75\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 1.0\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 4.25\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 4.5\right) = 1/36,$$

$$P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 1.25\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 1.5\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 3.75\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 4.0\right) = 1/18,$$

$$P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 1.75\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 2.0\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 2.25\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 2.5\right) = 1/12,$$

$$P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 2.75\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 3.0\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 3.25\right) = P\left(\frac{1}{X+Y} = 3.5\right) = 1/12.$$

In this case, it is found from calculation that

$$E_H \left(\frac{1}{X+Y} \right) = 0.38095238095238095238095238095238$$

$$\frac{1}{E_H \left(\frac{1}{X+Y} \right)} = 2.625$$

Note that

$$\frac{1}{E_H \left(\frac{1}{X} \right)} + \frac{1}{E_H \left(\frac{1}{Y} \right)} = 1.75 + 0.875 = 2.625 = \frac{1}{E_H \left(\frac{1}{X+Y} \right)}$$

4. CONCLUSION

The additive property of arithmetic expectation, termed as **Theorem (2.1)** expectation or simply expectation in standard literature in statistics, [8, 9, 11, 14, 16] can be summarized as

AE of Sum of Variable s = Sum of AE of Variable s

Theorem (2.1), describing the additive property of harmonic expectation, can be summarized as

$$\frac{1}{HE \text{ of } \left(\frac{1}{\text{Sum of Variable s}} \right)} = \text{Sum of } \left\{ \frac{1}{HE \text{ of } \left(\frac{1}{\text{Variable}} \right)} \right\} \text{s}$$

This is the rhythm lying in the additive property of harmonic expectation. For this reason, additive property of harmonic expectation has been termed here as the **Rhythmic Additive Property of Harmonic Expectation**.

It is to be mentioned that the additive property of harmonic expectation has here been derived in the case of a discrete random variable. Derivation of this property is to be done in the case of continuous random variable.

Like arithmetic expectation, there may be more properties of harmonic expectation. Study can be made on searching for these properties if exist.

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